

Expanding the Bumbuna¹ Hydro and Solar Power Systems in Sierra Leone

through Innovative Technology and Effective Financial Planning and Analysis (FINPLAN).

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Context and Aim

- ❑ Sierra Leone is currently experiencing a severe electricity crisis characterized by insufficient supply, frequent outages, and heavy reliance on fossil fuels, particularly through supply from Karpower.
- ❖ To address this issue, a case study has been conducted to explore the potential of integrating a **60 MW hydropower plant** with a **60 MW solar power plant**.
- ❖ The project aims to increase the capacity of the existing Bumbuna hydro facility from **50 MW** to **110 MW**, while also adding a **60 MW floating solar** installation at the same site.

Project Description and Financing

Technology	Hydro	Solar
1) Project Data		
Investment (USD'mn)	100	60
Capacity (MW)	60	60
Tariff (US\$cent/KWh)	8	8
Start year	2025	2025
Project Lifetime (yr)	25	40
Construction Period (yr)	3	2
2) Macroeconomic and Fiscal Data		
SL Inflation (%)	42.6	
US Inflation (%)	3.4	
Exchange Rate SL/USD	23	
Tax Rate (%)	15	
3) Financial Data		
Debt/Equity	70/30	
Proportion of Project Loan (%)	50	

Scenarios / Sensitivity Analysis

Scenario	Capacity Factor (MW)		Project Life time (yrs)		Tariff US cents/KWh	Tax Rate (%)
	Hydro	Solar	Hydro	Solar		
Baseline	45%	25%	40yr	25yr	8 US cent/KWh	0
Scenario 1	35%	20%	30yr	25yr	8 US cent/KWh	0
Scenario 2	35%	20%	30yr	25yr	6 US cent/KWh	15%

Results

Interpretations of Scenarios

- ***Baseline: 8 US cents/KWh with zero tax rate***
- ***Scenario 1: Normal tariff of 8 US cents/KWh with no tax***
- ***Scenario 2: Reduced tariff of 6 US cents/kWh with a 15% tax***

The results of the project suggest that the significant decrease in revenue in 2052 is due to the end of the solar panel's life. However, Scenarios 1& 2 show positive NPVs of NLe 30 & 60 million and IRR of 15% and 25% respectively. This indicates that the project is profitable and attractive.

Conclusions and Policy Insights

Conclusions	Policy Insights
<p>1. The result of Scenario 1 &2 shows positive NPVs of NLe 30 & NLe 60 million and IRR of 15% and 25% respectively . This indicates that the project is profitable and attractive.</p>	<p>1. The Government of Sierra Leone should promote renewable energy initiatives by providing more incentives (lower tariffs and concessions) to boost clean energy accessibility and affordability.</p>
<p>2. The results of the two scenarios suggest that the significant decrease in revenue and dividend is due to the end of the solar panel's life</p>	<p>2 . More advanced technology and investment should be deployed to improve the solar panel's efficiency, lifetime, capacity, revenue and returns.</p>

Thank You